

Experimental and Material Point Method simulations for determining the behaviour of Ti6Al4V during scratch test at high strain rates

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1. INTRODUCTION

Scratch testing has been a widely used technique to obtain valuable information about the mechanical properties of materials, including their hardness, adhesion, and wear resistance. Scratch tests have the advantage over tension, compression, or torsion tests to be a non-destructive technique that does not require complex geometries in its test specimen and can be performed with relative ease.

A main limitation of scratch tests is that they are typically performed under quasistatic conditions. While this may serve to suitably characterize the cracking and adhesion behaviour of coatings, it is not suitable for characterizing the behaviour of materials during machining processes or single abrasion events, as those processes involve strain rates that are several orders of magnitude higher.

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in using meshfree computational methods, such as Material Point Method (MPM) simulations, to model and analyse scratch tests (1,2). This work aims to build a complementary approach between experimental and simulated scratches with focus on high strain rates that can provide valuable insights into the mechanical behaviour of materials. Ti6Al4V serves as illustrative example, as it is an alloy with a wide range of applications ranging from aerospace to biomedical implants and whose behaviour during abrasive or erosive events at high strain rates is of high industrial relevance.

2. METHODS

2.1. Material Point Method simulations

MPM is particularly suitable to be used in problems that deal with large deformations; this so-called meshless technique is able to overcome some of the common issues that arise with FEM simulations, such as mesh distortion and the need of re-meshing.

In this work, the scratch simulations are performed using the SMD package (3) within LAMMPS (4) that provides an implementation of the Generalized Interpolation Material Point Method (GIMP). This method is then coupled with the viscoplastic Johnson-Cook material model.

2.2. High speed scratch test experiments

Experimental scratches were performed using a pendulum scratch test that allows velocities of ~6.5 m/s during the scratching process, using a Rockwell-C indenter and recording the forces during each scratch event with a piezoelectric transducer for further post-processing. The scratches were performed in each sample for depths between 10 to 50 μm to characterise a range of abrasive events.

3. RESULTS

The simulated profiles for the Ti6Al4V sample are shown in Figure 1 for three different scratch depths, the simulations were considered to be in good agreement with the experimental profiles, while providing insights into the scratching process and the stress distribution that cannot be obtained directly from the experimental setup. A particle size of 10 μm in the simulations was shown to be the most effective in terms of computational resources and accuracy in the results.

4. REFERENCES

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Figure 1. Simulated scratches with scratch depths of 10 μm, 20 μm, and 25 μm in Ti6Al4V